

D8.1 Data Management Plan

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BEYOND Consortium

	ROLE	NAME	Acronym	Country
1.	Coordinator	University of Oslo	UiO	Norway
2.	Partner	European Network of Research Ethics Committees	EUREC	Belgium
3.	Partner	High Council For The Evaluation of Research and Higher Education	HCERES	France
4.	Partner	French Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment	INRAE	France

5.	Partner	Oslo Metropolitan University	OsloMet	Norway
6.	Partner	Eurosis Federation of Finnish Learned Societies	TSV	Finland
7.	Partner	University of Central Lancashire-Cyprus	UCLanCY	Cyprus
8.	Partner	University of Helsinki	UH	Finland
9.	Partner	University of Humanistic Studies	UHS	The Netherlands
10.	Partner	University of Latvia	UL	Latvia
11.	Partner	University of Tartu	UTARTU	Estonia
12.	Partner	Stichting VUMC / The Embassy of Good Science	VUMC	The Netherlands
13.	AP	Trilateral Research LTD	TRI	UK
14.	AP	Heriot-Watt University	HWU	SCT

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1 Data Summary

The main goal of BEYOND is to robustly explore and advance individual and institutional responsibilities in research misconduct (RM) and in the promotion of research ethics and research integrity (RE/RI). BEYOND will achieve this goal by developing co-created, needs-andcase-based, streamlined, and best practices-based measures meant to engage, guide and equip research-related stakeholders through guidance and educational instruments.

To achieve the main goal, BEYOND is based on four key building blocks, which translates into specific objectives.

No	Specific Objectives	Time bound, measurable outputs
1	EXPLORE: Identify behavioral knowledge and needs through a state-of-the-art review of personal and institutional responsibilities on RE/RI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> An article on behavioral and organizational ethics, and moral psychology on the promotion of RE/RI and to their breaches Monitor and review cases of RM and QRPs An article on validated RM measurement instruments across the range of constructs of interest An article on interventions to improve RE/RI A report on socio-economic impact assessment of RM
2	EXPLORE & ENGAGE: Facilitate bottom-up and solution-oriented public consultations on RE/RI needs, knowledge, and perspectives on the efficacy of RE/RI interventions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organization of public consultation on RE/RI needs, knowledge, perspectives, and real-life experiences of RM List of stakeholders An article for a solution-oriented consultation design Recommendations from the analysis of the consultation process
3	EXPLORE & GUIDE: Design and test psychologically informed interventions as methodologies to promote RE/RI and address RM from the perspective of personal and institutional responsibilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A report on contextual sensitive framework of QRPs Design novel interventions (including nudges) to combat RM A report on the validation of interventions in vignette-based experiments

4	<p>EXPLORE & GUIDE: Develop methodologies to measure the short-, medium-, and long-term impact of RE/RI trainings on attitudes and behaviors of students and researchers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A report on the mapping of measurements methods and instruments for effects of RE/RI training 2 reports on methodologies aim to promote RE/RI • A report on tools for short-, medium- and long-term measurement of RE/RI training effects • A report on recommendations on how to evaluate short-, medium- and long-term effectiveness and impact of training interventions
5	<p>EQUIP & GUIDE: Provide guidance through a best-practice manual, guidelines that supplement standard operating procedures, and a 2030 roadmap towards improving RE/RI culture</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • List of stakeholder advisory board • A report on best practices manual for effective measures to promote RE/RI and address RM • A report on guideline to supplement existing standard operating procedures (DOPs) in RE/RI and RM • A report on RE/RI roadmap to 2030 to outlines RE/RI goals • An article on existing RE/RI guidelines and DOPs
6	<p>EQUIP & ENGAGE: Foster broad uptake of project outputs through strategic synergy building and the provision of training materials that supplement existing RE/RI training materials</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A report on mapping of training materials and tools for RE/RI education • A report on trainers guides to supplement existing training materials and tools • A report on training materials and tools for mentoring, supervision, leadership

This is the initial Data Management Plan (DMP) for the project, which will be updated periodically. Future updates will include more technical details such as file size and actual formats of the data generated.

2 Project Data

For some of the BEYOND outputs, data collection would be required. The project will gather data of varied formats—including text transcripts, images, quantitative data, qualitative data, data based on physiological markers, data from reviews of the literature, training sessions, stakeholder consultation meetings and co-creation workshops.

The types of the data that BEYOND will gather vary.

- There will be literature review data from published articles (academic publications) and grey literature (non-academic publications), scoping exercises, and reviews of cases, i.e., data from databases and resources that collate cases.
- Personal data from public consultation (citizen and stakeholder consultation meetings) and co-creation workshops, including personal and organizational details of research participants and expert stakeholders. Public consultation may also involve anonymous data collected via an online platform, as well as qualitative interviews conducted with stakeholders.
- Experimental and statistical data (from interventions and observations), qualitative data from stakeholder interviews, and a review of secondary data.
- Other data from training materials, best practices manuals and guidelines, and administrative and financial data will all be assembled.

BEYOND will hold stakeholder meetings. It is to be expected that the number of stakeholders in these meetings and workshops would vary depending on the need as well as the availability of stakeholders.

BEYOND will also utilise training sessions organised by and in collaboration with partner institutions to collect data on learning processes and outcomes.

The BEYOND Work Packages will use all the data gathered for the purposes specified in the BEYOND Description of Action, and BEYOND will strongly adhere to the FAIR principles and the data protection regulations.

To allow for the needed flexibility of BEYOND partners in gathering and storing data, data will be curated by the partner institution mainly responsible for the relevant tasks, on the condition that the repository is GDPR-compliant. The partner institution is responsible for ensuring this.

3 FAIR data

The data generated will be as open as possible and as restricted as necessary, and the data will be archived by the responsible partner institutions. Unless restricted by privacy and confidentiality considerations and GDPR requirements, data will also be published in FAIR data repositories, such as Zenodo, after going through

a data curation process. Repositories such as Zenodo use metadata schema and generate machine-actionable metadata that can be indexed by most search engines (including Datacite and Google Dataset Search) and other national data registers. Using this standard, data will be described comprehensively with extensive and rich metadata to ensure FAIRness. Digital items will also be assigned a DataCite DOI upon publication and accessed by their identifier using a free and standard communication protocol (HTTPS). Data under embargo can also be provided with a DOI or a private link for external partners to have access to it (e.g., journal article reviewers).

Some of the metadata elements that facilitate FAIRness include the title of the research project, the names of the author and co-authors, a description of the data, an abstract that summarizes the research, funding details (such as grant project name, acronym, and number), publication date, version number, categories that define the research discipline, keywords that describe the data, Digital Object Identifier (DOI), licensing information (Creative Commons), title and link to the related publication, and links to any reference or related content.

By including these metadata elements, data is searchable and discoverable, accessible to others who may want to use it, and that the information relating to the reuse is made clear. Additionally, a human-readable ReadMe file, which comprehensively discusses the digital item being archived, is a mandatory document required in the data curation process. Data generated by the project will be made publicly available following its completion using a CC-BY license, except for conditions stipulated in the Grant Agreement

4 Other Research Outputs

The Grant Agreement governs the research outputs of the project. To promote Open Science, scientific articles will be published in open access journals, and data resulting from the project will be archived as described above. This ensures that research outputs of the project are easily accessible and reusable by a variety of potential users, including other researchers, educators, policymakers, and members of the general public. Since the project is in its initial phase, and other research outputs that are of value may be generated as the project progresses, this part will also be updated in the next DMPs.

5 Data Security

For the duration of the project, data will be securely and confidentially stored in a GDPR-compliant storage solution. Partners with access to GDPR-compliant storage systems are responsible for data security. This is, for example, relevant to the University of Helsinki (WP4), where Red Cap will be used to store the data accumulated from different partner organisations for the educational intervention study and University of Latvia, where data from public consultation and stakeholder interviews will be stored. The coordinating institution offers project data storage in the UiO local network, if partners need it. This storage solution is approved for Red (Confidential/Sensitive) data in the Norwegian classification system.

UNDER REVIEW BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION